

Sustainable Environment: Challenges and Solution in Pakistan

Author's Details:

Muhammad Roman¹, Shahbaz Ali¹ Sarwan Khan¹, Ahmad Raza Shahid², Husnain Rauf³

School of Soil and Water Conservation, Beijing Forestry University, China.¹

Askari Farms & Seeds Depalpur, District Okara, Punjab, Pakistan.²

Christian-Alrechts-Universität zu Kiel, Plant breeding Institute, Germany.³

Abstract:

The achievement of sustainable development in the environment necessitates a holistic effort in all areas of society to meet the appropriate criteria. Current debates about urban sustainability not only tend to focus on carbon emissions, energy consumption, and waste management but also the role of facility managers in dealing the environmental problems towards sustainable development and environment. Inevitably, there is a need to specify the permissible building specific environmental that must be compatible with overall sustainability targets. This paper delineates the mitigation plan that can be adopted by facility managers to overcome environmental issues that may affect the total management, performance, and operation of development in Pakistan. This paper also described several environmental problems that occurred in Pakistan and gave some strategies that may help for a sustainable environment in Pakistan.

Keywords: Sustainable environment, environmental challenges, Strategies, Recommendations

1. Introduction:

Environmental protection has become a national issue as well as international issue in recent years. Though scientists and environmentalists have recognized the magnitude and significance of environmental problems for decades, it is only recently that the media has turned to highlight issues like Minamata disease (Japan), Bhopal tragedy (India), greenhouse effect, deforestation, global warming and waste generation. Creating sustainable development must be implemented as a reactive plan. World Business Council for Sustainable Development^[1] has defined sustainable development as “form of progress that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their needs.” Therefore, to make sustainable development and environment, tentative programmers and campaigns to enforce environment awareness must be emphasized as vital programmers prior to several cases due to poor environmental conditions. As mentioned by Tweed and Sutherland^[2], existing approaches to sustainable development tend to focus on technical issues, such as the reduction of energy consumption and environmental pollution. For example, in China, the government has taken comprehensive investment and measures to overcome environmental and pollution effects in their country. Inevitably, the global community has shown keen awareness and concern over environmental issues these past decades. This community includes the public, government, and the corporate world. Those formerly opposed to environmental conservation are slowly but surely becoming proponents advocating going to sustainable development. Therefore, reducing the burden of environmental impacts is necessary if development is to become sustainable.

However, it seems that programmers undertaken due to poor environmental conditions are a reactive approach; only implemented when there is an occurrence of a disaster. This conventional thinking needs to be changed as poor environmental conditions will leave bad effects on the global environment. Unplanned development and the public's low attitude are among the causes that constitute environmental problems, especially in developing countries^[3]. Even though environment protection has been emphasized in many countries like China, Japan, and the United Kingdom, but still there are several countries not allocate these issues as main

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priority solution or activities. Ecological sustainability is, in turn, a basic prerequisite for sustainable economic and social development. Without binding sub-targets for the different sectors, it will be all but impossible to move systematically towards a sustainable society^[4]. A combined pollution load (BOD, COD & TDS) in wastewater discharged to inland water bodies has been estimated at 28.6 (in 2010) to a projected value of 58.6 million tons/annum⁽⁶⁾. Degradation of water quality, both for human consumption and irrigation, due to industrial wastewater discharge with high pollution load and its resulting impacts on public health and environment are most obvious. In a recent SDPI survey of 38 polluted sites in the country, it was shocking to observe, wastewater from the industrial estates and industrial units being discharged into agriculture fields mostly for cash crops but also in a few, for food crops and vegetables, both on large and small scales⁽⁷⁾. Water and soil are known and well-established pathways for toxic chemicals (metals, non-metals & organics) getting into the food chain and ultimately into human bodies, besides, to a lesser extent through the air. Annex 1 describes the list of 37 industries identified and assessed by SDPI team in Punjab (25 in/around 7 cities), Khyber Pakhtunkhwa (5 in/around 3 cities) and Sindh (7 in/around 2 cities). Two polluted sites were identified and assessed in/around Islamabad⁽⁷⁾. Nine priority polluted sites for which immediate remediation actions are required are listed in Annex 2. Industrial chemicals manufacturing and use, obsolete pesticides stocks and hospital wastes are the main potential sources of hazardous wastes in the country. A substantial quantum of hazardous industrial wastes is also released by old/expired ship-breaking yards and non-formal industrial sector/SMEs, including very small-scale recycling units run by un-skilled and illiterate labor, which are scattered across the country. To the best of accessible information, district-based inventory of these by district/provincial EPAs are yet to be developed.

2. Key Environmental Issues and Challenges in Pakistan

In recent years Pakistan has experienced impressive real GD P growth accompanied by a sharp decline in poverty. However, human wellbeing is critically dependent on the continued availability of essential ecological services and natural resources. Pakistan's environment and natural resources are increasingly polluted and under stress. Pressing environmental concerns facing the country to relate broadly to the management of scarce natural resources (green issues), pollution and waste management (brown) and issues pertaining to the potential vulnerabilities to natural hazards and climate change. Pakistan's natural resources are increasingly under stress due to rapid population growth and environmentally unsustainable practices. Renewable freshwater resources are fast depleting pushing Pakistan into the category of water stressed countries. Freshwater flows in Pakistan's rivers have been substantially reduced by water diversion for agricultural irrigation in recent decades. Canal irrigation, due to low levels of efficiency has resulted in salinization, thus adversely affecting crop yields. Excessive and improper use of pesticides is destroying the natural biotic balance in agriculture soils and reducing the diversity of invertebrate fauna. The reported decline in the area under the natural forest cover has implications for essential ecological services, irrigation, and for biodiversity. Mangroves, the traditional breeding grounds for commercially important sea life, have also declined.

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Fig. (a) Pollution Index of Pakistan December 2018

Similarly, Pakistan's arid and semi-arid rangelands are extensively degraded, due to the large increase in livestock grazing. The trends and prospects for the future vary greatly depending on climatic conditions and social responses. Pollution due to a lack of effective management has emerged as a major environmental concern in Pakistan. Over the years Pakistan's growing energy consumption needs have resulted in its increased reliance on the imported fossil fuels. Its progress towards energy efficiency has been modest due to weak technical and institutional capacities. Measures such as the conversion of vehicles to cleaner fuels (CNG), no lead gasoline and low Sulphur diesel have been implemented but remain insufficient to prevent deteriorating in ambient air quality in the urban areas due to increasing vehicle numbers and their hazardous emissions. Indoor air pollution is a major cause of widespread chronic bronchitis and other respiratory infections in rural households and poor urban households that depend on biomass for cooking particularly in winters. Industrial discharges (of toxic and persistent pollutants) are contaminating some of the country's best soils and water resource.

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Fig. (b). Severe Water pollution in Punjab and Sindh Province, Pakistan.

Solid waste dumped on low-lying land or burnt pollutes groundwater or generates dust and carcinogenic pollutants with adverse health implications. The disposal of untreated urban sewage is contaminating fresh water sources for downstream users. Poor sanitation and hygiene and lack of access to safe drinking water supply are contributory factors to a high rate of diseases such as diarrhea in the country.

4.3 Air pollution- an emerging issue in Pakistan

Air pollution is a growing environmental problem day by day in Karachi, especially in the large metropolises. According to a World Bank report, "Karachi's urban air pollution is among the most severe in the world and it engenders significant damages to human health, and the economy "The inefficient use of energy, an increase in the number of vehicles used daily, an increase in unregulated industrial emissions and the burning of garbage and plastic have contributed the most to air pollution in urban areas. According to a recent study, Karachi's Environment Protection Department claims that the average level of pollution in big cities is approximately four times higher than the Organization's limits. These emissions have detrimental effects, including "respiratory diseases, reduced visibility, loss of vegetation and an effect on the growth of plants."One of the greatest contributors to air pollution is industrial activity. The inadequate air emission treatments and lack of regulatory control over industrial activity have contributed to the deterioration of ambient air quality in major cities.

In addition, the common practice of burning massive amounts of solid waste, including plastic and rubber, on street corners by the public, releases toxic gases, which are extremely harmful to residents in the area. Air pollutants can be transported across states and national boundaries, therefore pollutants produced by one country, as well have adverse impacts on the environment of neighboring countries

	Index Values	PM2.5 conc.	Lahore	Peshawar	Islamabad	Karachi
Good	0 to 50	0.0 – 12.0	2	1	0	4
Moderate	51 to 100	12.1 – 35.4	39	224	57	157
Sensitive	101 to 150	35.5 – 55.4	47	48	105	97
Unhealthy	151 to 200	55.5 – 150.4	101	87	143	50
Very Unhealthy	201 to 300	150.5 – 250.4	39	5	10	2
Hazardous	301 to 500	250.5 – 500	36	0	2	0
#nodata			101	0	48	55

Lahore has the worst air quality in Pakistan, with 2 blue sky days in 2017 with #Good air quality, and 36 days with #Hazardous air pollution.

Air Quality Index for Health impact as defined by the USA EPA. The Environmental Protection Agency of Pakistan (PK-EPA) recommended 15 µg/m³ as the safe level for yearly exposure, after which serious health effects occur. The WHO guideline value is 10 µg/m³.

Data: Pakistan Air Quality Initiative (PAQI) 01 January to 31 December 2017

Fig. (c). Air Quality of Major cities of Pakistan. (Pakistan Air Quality Initiative 2017).

Trans-boundary air pollution, which is also impacting some areas of Pakistan, as evident by increased fog in winter months, is an emerging environmental issue that demands critical attention. Down-wind areas of the countries are likely to be affected more than the upwind areas the impact of climate change on chemicals

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characteristics, hazardous wastes and sites and the resulting impacts on the environment and public health have been little realized in Pakistan and other developing countries. The high temperature and low precipitation would enhance volatile chemicals levels in the air, and the increased evaporation would enhance non-volatile chemicals levels in water bodies and soil. The low temperature and high precipitation/snowfall would transport back air pollutants to water bodies and land. Enhanced air, water, and land pollution due to climate change and in the event of a high flood, the spread of hazardous wastes dumps into cities/towns at the polluted sites could play havoc with the environment and health of the population of the climate change affected areas of the country.

1. Pakistan's Rising Air Pollution Crisis

According to the World Health Organization (WHO), over 4 million people around the world succumb to air pollution-related illnesses on an annual basis, due to toxic air quality levels that go well beyond the standard guidelines outlined by the WHO. In addition, the report also highlights countries such as China, India, Pakistan, and Bangladesh that have “increasing trends in PM_{2.5} exposure.” However, while China has made some improvement in tackling air pollution, India, Pakistan, and Bangladesh “have experienced the steepest increases in air pollution levels since 2010 and now present the highest sustained PM_{2.5} concentrations.” In Pakistan, without any government intervention or even social awareness campaigns – informing citizens how to protect themselves from the toxic smog – the past few years have seen an extraordinary rise in air pollution, particularly during the onset of winter. According to a report by *Lancet*, a medical journal, approximately 22 percent of deaths in Pakistan each year are attributed to air pollution. This led Abid Omar, a young entrepreneur based in Karachi, to initiate the Pakistan Air Quality Initiative (PAQI), which provides real-time data on air quality in the country. Having lived in Beijing, China, for a few years, Omar realized how imperative publicly available data was in instigating a much-needed call to action regarding China's air pollution issue. “I saw how [it] helped change the conversation there; how the Beijing government first claimed ignorance, then started monitoring air quality and making the data accessible to the public,” he said. “And finally, [how they] then started to implement policies that are trailblazing for excellence in environmental governance. “But on his home turf, Omar discovered that there was an alarming lack of data on air pollution levels in Pakistan. “When I saw that the government of Pakistan did not even have the equipment to measure air quality in 2016, I decided to set up my own air quality monitoring network. “After installing imported air quality monitors in the cities of Lahore, Islamabad, Peshawar, and Karachi, Omar says that through his platform, he was able to engage citizens who understood the gravity of the situation: The air in Pakistan truly does stand as an “invisible killer.”

Recommendations

The responsibility of the slow progress referred to above needs to be looked at the performance of the three main stakeholders to the environment issue, the government (MoE/EPAs), industrial sector (FPCCI, provincial & district CCI & industrial associations and representatives of civil society (NGOs & CBOs) and their constraints/limitations in meeting the challenge of a clean environment in the country. There seems to be a general impression of a lack of political will. The environment has not been among the priorities of the past or present government. Hardly any political party manifesto prominently speaks of environmental issues in the country. All along the government's preference has been a voluntary or carrot approach and not a strict or stick approach in regulating industrial pollution. Pakistan environmental protection council (PEPC), just meets once a year and sometimes even after a longer period, to monitor and expedite the development/implementation of environmental policies and programs in the country. The implementation of the approved environmental policies, action plan, program and projects on times take so long that the situation

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over the time changes drastically and these either may not remain feasible or needs to go through another time investing process of updates and revision, as evident by revised NEQs, Self-monitoring and reporting/SMART 2 program. The same need may arise for the national implementation plan (NIP) for phasing out persistent organic pollutants (POPs). Lack of capacity and capacity building, expertise, technical know-how, technical facilities, and human resource are other major constraints, not only for the government to enforce compliance but also for the industry to comply with.

In the early years of environmental policy and legislation development, industry through FPCCI, not only supported government initiatives but also played an important role as an active member of National Standards Committee and NEQs implementation committee. FPCCI not only agreed to payment of pollution charge but also proposed the amount of the base rate/pollution unit for non-compliance with NEQs. However, the government's response to the FPCCI proposed financial incentives (9) and lack of credit availability/facility for environmental technology or investment has not been up to FPCCI expectations. Even whereas, the industry seems willing to invest in pollution control measures, the information regarding key-turn appropriate, well tested and established technology, its cost, effectiveness, and durability have not been readily accessible. Establishment of "Provincial Sustainable Development Fund" to support industry with soft loan for the purchase of pollution control equipment and installation of industry specific "Joint Treatment Plants" was agreed upon (9) both by the government and the industry but it could not be well institutionalized due to diversified opinion regarding its operating mechanism and delayed power delegation of the same to the provincial governments. Civil society can also play a vital role towards industrial pollution control by building awareness, understanding and concern within all stakeholders and sections of society, providing relevant information and help to marginalized and vulnerable groups (women, children, elderly & sick) and by carrying out national and local campaigns and projects that contributes to protecting environment and minimizing public exposure to toxic industrial releases/hazardous waste sites. Civil society needs to be involved to the extent possible, both at the policy development and implementation phases, as is now made obligatory to the national governments party to Stockholm Convention on POPs, Strategic Approach to International Chemicals Management (SAICM) and the under-negotiation UNEP draft text of the legally binding instrument on mercury phase-out.^[10]

Conclusion

As a conclusion, facility managers, innovators, building designers, and other built environment consultants should concern with environmental protection and sustainability as to re-evaluate and reconsider national, local and development policies and training activities. It can be seen that poor environmental conditions are occurred due to several factors such as the general lack of environmental concern, lack of environmental plans, policies, and activities. With the increase in awareness of environmental issues, the level of environmental disclosure and stakeholder demands for environmental information is increasing. It is recommended that in order to achieve meaningful improvement, facility managers must obtain adequate knowledge and develop appropriate concern for environmental issues. In addition, hotel managers should be eager to allocate the necessary funds to develop and implement state-of-the-art environmental programs. One initiative undertaken by our government is the adoption of the internationally recognized ISO 14001. The environmental management standard is also an important part of any environmental protection plan, policy, and practice. Such international standards can help a developer or any organizations to establish environmental protection programs and integrate them into a coherent framework, thereby enhancing relationships with government agencies, consumer groups, communities, and environmentally conscious investors.

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